

Solar Polygeneration Collector for Combined Heat, Power, Hydrogen Fuel and Wastewater Treatment

Guidelines on the potential of Industrial Wastewaters as sources of sacrificial agents for photocatalytic H₂ production

Prepared by:

Associação do Instituto Superior Técnico para a Investigação e o
Desenvolvimento (IST-ID)

Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia, I.P. (LNEG)

Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas
(CIEMAT)

University of Bolonha (UNIBO)

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Nomenclature

Acronym	Meaning
Abs	Absorvance
AOP	Advanced Oxidation Processes
D_p	Average Pore diameter
E_g	Band gap
S_{BET}	BET surface area
BOD	Biochemical Oxygen Demand
COD	Chemical Oxygen Demand
C/F	Coagulation - Flocculation
CB	Conduction Band
S_c	Cumulative surface area
DOC	Dissolved Organic Carbon
EDTA	Ethylenediamine tetracetic acid
GC-MS	Gas Chromatography coupled to Mass Spectrometry
HPLC	High-Performance Liquid Chromatography
HER	Hydrogen Evolution Rate
IWW	Industrial Wastewater
MWW	Municipal Wastewater
NPs	Nanoparticles
NIR	Near-Infrared Radiation

NTU	Nephelometric Turbidity Unit
OER	Oxygen Evolution Reaction
PVT	Photovoltaic-Thermal
ROS	Reactive Oxygen Species
SA	Sacrificial Agent
η_{STH}	Solar-To-Hydrogen efficiency
TDS	Total Dissolved Solids
TOC	Total Organic Carbon
TSS	Total Suspended Solids
UV	Ultraviolet radiation
VB	Valence Band
Vis	Visible radiation
V_p	Volume

Executive Summary

The SPECTRUM project aims to design, develop, prototype, and test lab-scale solar collectors that effectively utilise the entire solar spectrum to cogenerate heat, electricity and hydrogen. Hydrogen production will result from the remediation of industrial wastewater using solar power and low cost nanostructured TiO₂-based photocatalysts. This deliverable D1.1 proposes comprehensive guidelines on the use of industrial wastewater (IWW) as a source of sacrificial agents (SA) for solar-driven photocatalytic hydrogen production. It evaluates the dual potential of this approach to simultaneously generate renewable hydrogen and treat wastewater, aligning with circular economy and EU decarbonisation goals. The report reviews the fundamentals of photocatalysis, the role of SA, and how various IWW compositions — rich in organic compounds like alcohols, sugars, acids, and sulphides — can enhance hydrogen generation. Key parameters influencing the viability and efficiency of this method include organic content (COD, BOD), pH, dissolved oxygen, turbidity, light-scattering compounds, and the presence of interfering compounds. Case studies using real IWW from food, olive oil, and fermentation industries demonstrate promising hydrogen yields and pollutant reduction. The report also outlines pre-treatment steps, logistical considerations, and presents a step-by-step decision-making framework for identifying the best possible IWW candidates to be used as sources of SA in photocatalytic hydrogen production.

1. Introduction

1.1. Benefits of producing H₂ through photocatalysis

With a strong push towards decarbonisation, the production of hydrogen (H₂) is one of the main topics of the century, as it is a clean and renewable energy carrier or fuel offering zero-emission potential when produced using renewable energy sources such as solar or wind energy¹.

To improve the cost-effectiveness of photocatalytic hydrogen production as a green energy vector and sustainable alternative to fossil fuels, it is necessary to enhance the efficiency, durability, recyclability, and cost of new photocatalytic materials.

Photocatalytic H₂ production through water splitting is a sustainable, renewable and promising technology, particularly when powered by sunlight. Various types of catalysts can be used in this process, such as metal oxides, where the most common is titanium dioxide (TiO₂), metal sulphides, carbon nitrides and perovskites². Each of these catalysts offers distinct advantages and limitations; however, TiO₂-based photocatalysts are the most widely used in photocatalytic water splitting due to their strong oxidation power, chemical inertness, non-toxicity and low-cost of TiO₂^{2,3}.

In the past decade, various strategies have been applied to enhance the low efficiency of bare TiO₂ as a photocatalyst for H₂ production due to fast hole-photogenerated electrons recombination and wide band gap (~3.2 eV). Recent developments include the use of noble metals, mainly platinum, as co-catalysts, the development of TiO₂ composites with carbon materials (biochar, graphene, carbon nanotubes, carbon nitrides), and TiO₂ doping with non-metal elements such as nitrogen, sulphur, and boron⁴. One of the key factors for photocatalytic hydrogen production viability is to avoid the use of platinum due to its high cost and scarcity. The replacement of platinum with non-precious metals, such as copper, iron, nickel, and cobalt⁵ is still an ongoing challenge.

1.2. Mechanism of photocatalytic water splitting

The solar photocatalytic hydrogen production process involves several steps, as illustrated in Figure 1. First, the photocatalysts (usually a semiconductor material) absorb photons from the solar light irradiation with energy higher than its band gap⁴. The absorbed photons excite electrons in the photocatalysts, moving them to the conduction band (CB) and creating an electron-hole pair (e⁻/h⁺). The electrons on the CB are transferred to the surface of the catalyst and reduce protons (H⁺) to produce H₂ (Equation 1). This reaction is known as the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction (HER).

The holes generated on the catalyst's surface will act as active sites where water decomposes into oxygen and protons (Equation 2), also known as the Oxygen Evolution Reaction (OER)⁶.

Figure 1: Simplified mechanism of a platinum-doped TiO₂-based photocatalytic reaction for water splitting⁶.

1.3. Enhancement of photocatalysis with sacrificial agents

Photocatalytic hydrogen evolution can be enhanced by using SA. These chemical compounds are added to the reaction system to act as electron donors to the catalyst, thereby improving the HER. They also function as hole scavengers, selectively removing photoexcited holes, thereby decreasing the recombination rate of photoexcited charge carriers and increasing the charge separation efficiency. Selecting an appropriate sacrificial reagent necessitates meticulous consideration of its chemical compatibility with the photocatalyst. Controlling the concentration of the sacrificial agent and reaction parameters is essential for maximising the efficiency of hydrogen production.

Various compounds have been reported as possible SA as electron donors in water splitting including alcohols such as methanol⁷⁻¹¹, ethanol¹¹, glycerol^{8,11,12} and various other alcohols^{8,11,13}, saccharides and sugars such as glucose^{11,13,14}, sucrose^{15,16}, and xylose¹⁵, cellulose¹⁷, aromatic hydrocarbons such as naphthalene¹⁸, sulphide compounds^{7,16,19,20} such as Na₂S and Na₂SO₃, amines such as methylamine¹⁵, and triethanolamine^{8,13}, several carboxylic acids, such as lactic acid^{13,15} and formic acid¹⁵, ammonia¹⁵, and even EDTA⁷.

Short-chain alcohols, as aforementioned, are typically the SA selected for use with TiO₂ based photocatalysts^{21,22}. These alcohols are predominantly regarded as the gold standard for catalyst development and optimisation. They react with hydroxyl radicals and holes formed on the photocatalyst surface, making them optimal for this process. Different studies, mostly involving aqueous solutions of SA (synthetic mixtures), have

been carried out to assess the efficiency of these sacrificial agents in photocatalytic processes and their optimal concentration range. Naimah *et al.*²³ investigated the impact of different alcohols on hydrogen formation, observing that the efficiency decreases in the following order: glycerol > ethylene glycol > methanol > propylene glycol > n-propanol. In contrast, López *et al.*²⁴ tested with higher concentrations of SA, which yielded different results when compared with other studies and suggested an alternative efficiency ranking: methanol > ethanol > ethylene glycol > glycerol. The most commonly reported concentration range is 1.4-2.5 M, as it yields the best results for producing H₂^{13,25,26}.

Saccharides are also very common and efficient SA. Glucose has been reported both as a hole scavenger and a carbon source. Typically, it is usually used in low molar concentrations, around 0.1 M¹³, to account for their high molecular weight. Additionally, another study explored using other saccharides such as arabinose, fructose and cellobiose with a low concentration of 0.02 M²⁷.

Finally, carboxylic acids, including formic and oxalic acids, can act as electron donors, enhancing the formation of H₂ and the conversion of CO₂ in the photocatalytic process. These acids are typically used in low concentrations, around 0.1 M^{13,27}.

To summarise the above points, Table 1 presents the most used sacrificial agents by chemical category, along with their typical concentration values in studies using synthetic mixtures.

Table 1: Sacrificial agents and their typical concentration, per category.

Category	Compound	Concentration
Alcohols	glycerol ethylene glycol methanol isopropanol propylene glycol n-propanol	0.5M ²⁸ , 1.4 - 2.5 M ^{13,25,26}
Saccharides	glucose arabinose fructose cellobiose	0.1 M ^{13,27} and 0.02 M ²⁷
Carboxylic acids	formic acid oxalic acid	0.1 M ^{13,27}
Amine	triethanolamine	0.1 M ¹³
Sulphite/sulphide	sodium sulphite sodium sulphide	0.1 M ¹³

1.4. Using IWW as a source of sacrificial agents for H₂ cogeneration

Depending on the type of industrial processes and even within the same industrial process, IWW streams vary significantly in composition, often requiring customised treatment strategies.

Instead of requiring an additional compound to be used as SA, one emerging concept aligned with the circular economy concept is sourcing these SA from various wastewaters^{3,10,29–32}. Since many organic pollutants found in domestic or IWW are suitable candidates to act as SA, photocatalytic H₂ production from wastewaters merges solar energy harvesting with wastewater valorisation, addressing two challenges simultaneously: remediation of these pollutant organic compounds in wastewater and the generation of green hydrogen^{33,34}. Lanterna *et al.*³⁵ even observed this synergistic possibility using river water containing dissolved organic matter³¹.

In addition to acting as SA for hydrogen evolution, many organic pollutants in wastewater can be simultaneously degraded during the photocatalytic process due to the action of reactive species such as hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$) and superoxide anions ($\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$). As schematically illustrated in Figure 2, these reactive species are formed in the valence band (oxidation site) and conduction band (reduction site), respectively. Consequently, these species react with oxidising pollutants, ultimately reducing them to CO₂ and inorganic species^{3,18,32,36}

Figure 2: Mechanism of simultaneous photocatalytic hydrogen production and pollutant degradation³⁶.

IWW refers to the waterborne waste produced by various industrial activities, including manufacturing processes, mineral extraction, power generation, and water and

wastewater treatment. They often contain various polluting elements, including high levels of organic compounds, which are often expressed in terms of their Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) or Total Organic Carbon (TOC), as well as their biodegradable organic load, typically given as Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD). IWW often poses significant environmental problems due to its high nutrient content (nitrogen and phosphorus) and frequent presence of toxic compounds or emerging pollutants, such as heavy metals and persistent chemical compounds. Other critical parameters include suspended solids, colour, odour, and either a strongly acidic or alkaline pH.

The treatment and discharge of IWW are primarily regulated by the Industrial Emissions Directive (2010/75/EU)³⁷ and the revised Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (2024/3019)³⁸, which now impose stricter limits on industrial wastewater discharge and extend the producer responsibility to quaternary treatment. Therefore, in situ remediation technologies can offer a valuable means for pollution control, and a solar photocatalytic process coupled with hydrogen production can become an attractive low-carbon solution.

In fact, significant advances in catalytic processes for wastewater treatment, including advanced oxidation processes (Figure 3), that consist in the degradation of pollutants through the generation of strongly reactive species such as hydroxyl radicals, have been reported for water treatment due to their effectiveness in degrading organic and inorganic pollutants^{39,40}.

There are several key advantages of photocatalytic H₂ production from wastewater^{34,41}. This includes: a dual functionality by degrading organic pollutants while generating H₂ (e.g., Co₃O₄/TiO₂ systems degrade pharmaceuticals like ciprofloxacin with 95% efficiency and produce H₂ concurrently)³⁴; low-cost feedstocks where IWW can replace expensive pure sacrificial agents and scalability since modular reactors can be deployed near wastewater sources, reducing transport costs.

Several factors influence the efficiency of this process, namely, the type of catalyst, the presence of dopants or impurities, the degree of aggregation of the catalyst, surface area, and porosity⁴². Secondly, the matrix of the aqueous solution, especially when using IWW, is equally crucial due to various factors, such as, the presence of compounds that poison or interfere with the catalytic reaction, intrinsic chemical or physical characteristics of the IWW that may hinder light transmission or alter chemical reactions and especially the hydrogen production yield.

Figure 3: Example of an advanced oxidation process (AOP) for wastewater treatment using photocatalytic reactions¹⁹.

1.5. Report aims and objectives

Aiming for the successful development of solar photocatalytic technology with simultaneous hydrogen production and IWW treatment - while addressing both its potential opportunities and ways to overcome its limitations - SPECTRUM's first task is to review the available literature to establish the criteria for assessing the suitability of various IWW for photocatalytic H₂ cogeneration. This is achieved through this deliverable, whose objective is to identify a set of guidelines regarding the key characteristics of IWW best suited for the photocatalytic process, maximising the H₂ cogeneration yield. These guidelines will be helpful for the development of SPECTRUM's objectives and further the development of any process combining water splitting for hydrogen production with wastewater treatment.

A comprehensive literature review, along with various project meetings, has led to the identification of the key IWW characteristics that can enhance or impact the photocatalytic process and hydrogen production yield (section 2), such as the influence of pH, the presence of inorganic ions, the effect of the dissolved oxygen and the organic load of IWW. Then, a review of available studies using real wastewater is summarised and discussed (section 3). Finally, this document compiles various aspects related to the logistics and availability of IWW, along with suggestions on possible industrial sectors that could most benefit from this technology, leading to a decision-making tool to help select the best possible IWW candidates (section 4).

2. IWW key characteristics and their effect on the photocatalytic process with hydrogen cogeneration

When designing a solar photocatalytic system for hydrogen generation from IWW, it is essential to consider several intrinsic factors related to the photocatalysts used and extrinsic factors related to the matrix or system design. These factors affect the kinetics and influence the overall efficiency of the solar photocatalytic process⁴². Whilst there are numerous studies on catalyst design and optimisation, this section focuses on the various possible extrinsic factors related to the complexity of a matrix, such as IWW, in the photocatalytic process.

This section first provides an overview of the IWW's typical characteristics and composition parameters. Also, it discusses the effect of some of the most important extrinsic factors, from the presence of SA to parameters.

The first factor is the presence and nature of different organic pollutants that can act as SA on the hydrogen production rate in water splitting⁴¹. Another important factor is the penetration, wavelength, and intensity of the light, as these will affect the activation of the catalysts and, therefore, the overall efficiency of the reaction. In addition to these, the activity of the photocatalyst can be influenced by various physicochemical parameters, including pH, conductivity, salinity, dissolved oxygen, organic load, and the temperature of the medium^{8,42}.

Finally, this section provides an overview of key performance parameters to consider when designing a successful photocatalytic system for wastewater treatment and hydrogen production.

2.1. Typical industrial wastewater characteristics and composition

The primary objective of treating industrial wastewater is to mitigate its potential environmental impact on natural water bodies. This involves several key priorities. One of the main concerns is the prevention of anoxic conditions in aquatic ecosystems. This is achieved by removing compounds such as organic matter, whose microbial decomposition consumes dissolved oxygen and generates greenhouse gases and unpleasant odours. Another important aim is to prevent eutrophication, which occurs due to the presence of excess nutrients, such as nitrogen and phosphorus. These nutrients promote excessive growth of plants and algae, reducing light penetration and disrupting the ecological balance of water bodies.

In addition to ecological concerns, aesthetic and physical changes to the water must also be addressed. Suspended solids and colloidal matter contribute to turbidity, which not

only impairs the natural appearance of water but also limits photosynthesis and leads to sediment accumulation and further odour problems. A final, yet critical, goal is to protect both aquatic and human health by removing compounds that are toxic, persistent, anthropogenic, or otherwise harmful. These substances pose risks through direct toxicity, environmental dispersion, and long-term bioaccumulation.

Industrial wastewater is typically characterised using parameters like those used in the assessment of domestic wastewater. These include measurements of the oxidisable organic matter content, typically determined as COD or TOC. Biochemical oxygen demand, measured over five days and referred to as BOD₅, is also often determined to estimate the biodegradability of the organic load.

Additional physical and chemical characteristics are frequently measured to gain a more complete understanding of the wastewater composition. For instance, pH is used to assess whether the wastewater is acidic or alkaline, while conductivity indicates the total concentration of dissolved ions. Total suspended solids (TSS) and turbidity measurements provide insight into the presence of particulate matter, including both solids and colloids.

Depending on the origin and type of industrial wastewater, further compositional analysis may be required, as presented in Table 2. This may include the identification of nutrient compounds containing phosphorus and nitrogen, which are relevant to eutrophication, as well as specific priority pollutants such as heavy metals, aromatic compounds, or other substances known to be persistent, harmful, or toxic. In some cases, the presence of pathogenic or genetically modified microorganisms and viruses must also be considered. Table 2 presents an overview of some of the main pollutants produced by some industries.

Within the scope of the SPECTRUM project, the photocatalytic processes under study are primarily focused on decreasing COD and BOD using IWW that would contain a low content of suspended solids. This process may also be effective in targeting certain inorganic compounds, including sulphides and amines, which are often present in specific types of industrial effluent such as in IWW from tanneries, paper and pulp and eventually oil refining. A high presence of TSS and organic compounds in the form of COD or BOD is singled out as these are two important characteristics for a potential successful use of IWW for photocatalytic hydrogen generation^{43,44}.

IWW exhibit a wide distribution of compositions, characteristics, flows and daily, seasonal and yearly patterns across different industries. Therefore, it is difficult to determine a unified set of typical characteristics for the different types of industrial effluents. However, for most industrial operations, there will be a water supply stream and a wastewater or aqueous side-stream that, even when water reuse or recycling loops exist, part of it will always contribute to the overall wastewater produced by that industrial unit.

Table 2: Key pollutants of various examples of IWW.

Industry	TSS	COD, BOD	Major pollutants
Canning	Yes	Yes	High in suspended solids, colloidal products and dissolved organic matter, such as carbohydrates and proteins
Dairy	Yes	Yes	High in dissolved organic matter, such as lactose, and in suspended solids
Tannery	Yes	Yes	High total solids, hardness, salt sulphides, chromium, pH, precipitated lime and BOD ₅ that includes carbohydrates, proteins and dyes
Brewery	---	Yes	High in dissolved organic solids, containing nitrogen and fermented starches, carbohydrates or their products; may also contain colour
Oil and refinery	---	Yes	High dissolved salts from field, high BOD ₅ , odour, phenol and sulphur compounds from refinery; oils and various petrochemicals, sludge
Mining	Yes	---	Suspended solids, metals, acids and salts
Electronic	---	Yes	Organic chemicals, metals and metal ores, COD
Textile	Yes	Yes	Highly alkaline, coloured, COD, temperature, high suspended solids
Meat	Yes	Yes	High in dissolved and suspended organic matter, blood, other proteins and fats
Fish	Yes	Yes	Very high BOD ₅ , total organic solids, oils and grease, and colour
Pulp and paper	Yes	---	High or low pH, colour, high suspended, colloidal and dissolved solids

Despite this significant variability, some general classifications relevant to the goals of this report can be made. Firstly, industrial wastewater can be divided into two main categories: those primarily containing inorganic compounds and those primarily containing organic compounds⁴³.

Industries in coal, steel, and non-metallic minerals production and those engaged in metal processing (e.g., electroplating plants) predominantly generate wastewater containing inorganic compounds such as various metals and inorganic salts^{43,44}.

All other industries generate either organic-rich or miscellaneous organic/inorganic wastewaters^{43,44}. For photocatalytic hydrogen cogeneration and considering the nature of sacrificial agents discussed in Section 1.3, the most relevant types of IWW are those containing organic pollutants or, in some cases, inorganic pollutants such as sulphides.

The second key distinction is the concentration of these compounds. Some wastewaters, such as those from the chemical sector, contain only a few compounds but at high concentrations. In contrast, others, like those from the food, pulp or paper industries⁴³, contain a wide range of compounds at lower concentrations. For the SPECTRUM project, both types of IWW could be considered valuable. On the one hand, a “purer” stream with an interesting organic load, such as alcohols, would likely offer fewer interferences and potentially higher hydrogen yields. Additionally, dilution remains an option if the concentration of sacrificial agents is too high. On the other hand, a mixture of less concentrated compounds, provided they collectively possess electron donor potential, could also be suitable.

IWW vary widely in composition, characteristics, flow rates, and temporal patterns—daily, seasonal, and annual—across different sectors, as shown in Table 3. As a result, it is difficult to define a single set of representative characteristics for all types of industrial effluents. Nonetheless, in most industrial operations, there is typically both a water supply stream and a wastewater or aqueous side-stream. Even in systems where water reuse or recycling is practised, a portion of this stream inevitably contributes to the total wastewater output of the facility.

Despite this variability, some general classifications relevant to this report can be identified. Industrial wastewaters are commonly divided into those predominantly containing inorganic compounds and those primarily composed of organic compounds⁴³. Industries such as coal and steel production, non-metallic mineral processing, and metal finishing (e.g., electroplating) tend to produce wastewater rich in inorganic substances, including metals and salts^{43,44}.

In contrast, all other industries generate effluents that are either rich in organic matter or that contain a mixture of organic and inorganic pollutants^{43,44}. For photocatalytic hydrogen cogeneration and considering the sacrificial agent characteristics discussed in Section 1.3, the most relevant types of IWW are those containing organic compounds, or in some cases, inorganic pollutants such as sulphides.

A second key distinction relates to pollutant concentration. Some wastewaters, particularly from the chemical sector, contain only a few compounds but at relatively high concentrations, as observed on the data presented in Table 3. Others, such as those from the food, pulp, or paper industries, tend to include a broader mix of compounds present at lower concentrations⁴³. Both types of wastewaters can be of interest in this project. A more compositionally “pure” stream—rich in specific organics such as alcohols—may present fewer interferences and offer higher potential hydrogen yields. If concentrations are too high, dilution remains a viable strategy. Conversely, more complex mixtures with lower concentrations could also be suitable, provided the combined constituents exhibit sufficient electron-donor potential.

Table 3: Key IWW parameters for different examples of food industry IWW.

	Distillery ^{43,45}	Tomato processing (peak) ^{43,45}	Tomato processing (off-peak) ^{43,45}	Olive oil ⁴⁶	Citrus processing ⁴⁷	Winery ⁴⁸	Meat processing ⁴⁹
pH	3-5	6-8	6-8	5-6	3-5	5	---
BOD (g/L)	0.3-1	0.5-1.1	0.03-0.06	13.4-68	---	3.3	0.2-4.6
COD (g/L)	0.8-3	---	---	16.5-170	5-27	7.8	0.2-50.7
TSS	0.3-1.3	0.006-0.1	0.002	11.5-110*	---	1	12
Abs (245 nm)	0.4-2.3	0.2-0.8	0.2-0.9	---	---	---	---
Conductivity (mS)	---	---	---	5-81	---	2.2-3.5	---

A third important distinction concerns operational variability, which leads to changes in both wastewater flow and composition. Industries such as chemical manufacturing, pharmaceuticals, and certain food processing sectors that operate in batch mode often produce sudden, irregular discharges of wastewater. In contrast, industries that run continuous processes typically exhibit relatively stable flow rates and more consistent effluent compositions. Regardless of the operational mode, specific process stages—such as start-up, shutdown, and cleaning—can also lead to abrupt fluctuations in flow and changes in wastewater characteristics. These phases may introduce compounds such as disinfectants containing chlorides, which could be particularly undesirable in photocatalytic processes due to their potential to interfere with catalytic activity or produce harmful by-products.

Finally, as exemplified in Table 4, many industries operate under seasonal production modes, either due to the availability of raw materials or fluctuations in product demand, which might affect the feasibility of using solar energy to treat the resulting IWW.

 Table 4: Seasonality of various food processing industries in the Northern hemisphere. Grey scale goes from darker (peak production) to white (none to negligible production).⁵⁰⁻⁵²

Industry type	Months of the year											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Olive oil	Dark	White	Light	Light	Dark	Dark						
Milk	Dark	Dark	Dark	Dark	Dark	Light						
Tomato	White	White	White	White	White	White	Light	Dark	Dark	Light	White	White
Citrus	Dark	Dark	Dark	Dark	Dark	Light	Light	Light	Light	Dark	Dark	Dark
Wine	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	Dark	Dark	Dark	White

Based on the abovementioned characteristics, assessing and reviewing existing evidence on how these factors influence photocatalytic hydrogen cogeneration is crucial. The first factor is the presence and nature of different organic pollutants that can act as SA and positively impact the hydrogen production rate in water splitting⁵³. Then, one key factor is the penetration, wavelength and intensity of the light, as this will affect the activation of the catalysts and, therefore, the overall efficiency of the reaction. Several constituents in IWW can alter light penetration or scattering, such as suspended solids or colloids, colour, surfactants, foam or air bubbles, and various chemical compounds, in addition to the quantity and dispersion of the photocatalysts themselves. Besides these, the activity of the photocatalyst can be influenced by many of the physicochemical IWW parameters, such as pH, conductivity, salinity, dissolved oxygen, organic load, and temperature of the medium^{53,54}. These are discussed in the following sub-sections.

2.2. Sacrificial agents for wastewater splitting

As IWW contains numerous compounds beyond just SA, it remains unclear how the SA will selectively be used for hydrogen production. It is also unclear what will happen to the other oxidisable compounds in the wastewater and how that will affect the overall reaction efficiency.

Additionally, it is also important to ensure a not-so-low concentration (< 0.1 M), as it will reduce the rate of the reaction without enough hole scavenging⁵⁵. Besides that, higher concentrations (> 1 M) do carry some other constraints regarding light absorption by the sacrificial agent or even light scattering when there are compounds in suspension⁵⁶.

Even though possible SA are present in IWW, few studies have applied solar wastewater splitting directly to real wastewater samples (see Table 7) and many available studies use model wastewaters supplemented with various dyes^{9,32}. For different industries it is also observed variability on the type of SA present in its IWW. Some of the key SA of different industrial sectors are referenced in Table 5.

Table 5: Examples of industrial sectors and the key sacrificial agents^{33,57}.

Industry	Wastewater Type	Key SA
Rice Processing	Effluent from milling	Saccharides, cellulose
Brewery/Dairy	Fermentation byproducts	Lactose, ethanol
Olive Oil	Mill wastewater	Phenols, lipids
Wine	Winery wastewater	Ethanol, glucose and fructose, organic acids (lactic, tartaric, citric, malic, and succinic), and glycerin

In a yet-to-be-published preprint, Zhang *et al.* studied the simultaneous degradation of various dyes and the HER in a β -cyclodextrin polymer/titanium dioxide ($\text{TiO}_2/\beta\text{-CDP}$) photocatalyst system with platinum as a co-catalyst under solar light irradiation and with 10% methanol as SA. They observed approximately double the H_2 production rate in pure water plus SA compared to the one in the presence of the dye eosin Y, suggesting that the dye degradation diverted some electrons to produce from oxygen the necessary $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ radical species⁵¹. This suggests that a trade-off may exist between the HER and the pollutant's degradation, in which case the system's overall efficiency should consider the combined impact of both outcomes.

Another study by Li *et al.*⁵⁸ investigated the effect of coexisting substances in the photocatalytic hydrogen generation using glycerol wastewater. It appears that this effect varies significantly depending on the chemical redox properties of the compounds. Methanol and iron (Fe^{3+}) significantly enhance the hydrogen production yield due to their role as hole scavengers and the additional generation of hydroxyl radicals, which further degrade glycerol in the case of iron. On the other hand, compounds such as sodium stearate and copper ions reduce the reaction yield, in the first case possibly due to pH inhibition and in the second case due to Cu^{2+} ions competing for the electrons to be reduced into Cu^+ or Cu species.

2.3. Organic Load parameters

The organic load poses a great deal in developing the photocatalytic process. As mentioned before, much of this organic load will be integrated into the various reactions as sacrificial agents, thus benefiting the process. However, the variability of the organic load, both in terms of quantity and composition, in IWW presents a challenge when selecting suitable IWW⁵⁹.

Several parameters need to be studied concerning the organic load: BOD, COD, TDS and TSS.

The literature presents various concentration ranges of COD, particularly for synthetic wastewater (20-500 mg/L). Real IWW exhibits a much broader range of COD concentrations (e.g., 0-1000 mg/L), though some studies in the literature have reported some cases where this parameter reaches significantly higher values⁶⁰.

It is essential to verify the concentration ranges of these parameters, as high contents of organic load can significantly influence the process. The penetration of light radiation is crucial in the process, and high levels of organic load reduce the amount of radiation that can reach the catalyst surface, therefore reducing both the production of H_2 and the photocatalytic removal efficiency⁶¹. However, lower concentrations also negatively

impact the process efficiency due to the absence of organic matter, which can act as a sacrificial agent.

2.4. Light-absorbing/scattering compounds

Several studies have examined the influence of various IWW parameters, including the absorption and transmission of light in aqueous mediums, primarily applied to other research fields, specifically the use of UV light for wastewater disinfection⁶⁴.

The main relevant factor is the presence of suspended solids, colloidal particles and overall turbidity^{16,64,65}. Suspended particles are generally larger than 1.2 μm and are often settleable, whereas colloid particles are smaller, varying from 0.01 to 1.0 μm ⁶⁴. These can include organic particles such as food residues, bacterial flocs and fats or inorganic particles, including metal-based particles, various precipitates, clays and silts. For instance, dairy IWW will contain colloidal fat and protein-based micelles, which contribute to its turbidity. These particles will interfere with light penetration and transmission, making it difficult to reach the photocatalytic particles and, therefore, reducing the reaction's efficacy. Small colloidal particles under 0.45 μm seem to affect light transmission particularly⁶⁴.

The presence of surfactants is another potentially significant factor. Surfactants are frequently present in IWW due to their widespread use in cosmetics and pharma, dyes, textiles and leather tanning industries. These substances may cause bubbles or foam that can scatter light and thereby diminish light transmission, and can also form micelles that encapsulate viable SA, reducing their availability for enhancing the HER⁶⁶.

IWW also frequently contains dissolved compounds that can absorb light and affect light transmission and intensity. Examples include coloured compounds such as organic and inorganic dyes, complex organic compounds such as humic acids, various metals such as iron or chromium⁵⁰ and many organic compounds containing aromatic groups or double bonds such as toluene or benzene⁶². These can result not only from textiles or dye-producing companies but also from industries such as food, distilleries, or even landfill leachates⁶³. In addition, compounds such as humic acids are also prevalent in the agri-food industries, as well as in the tanning, paper, and mining sectors, and these are also chromogenic⁶². These compounds will absorb UVA and visible light, which, especially in solar-based photocatalytic applications, reduces light transmission and hence the energy available for the catalytic reaction, thereby decreasing the overall process efficiency. Speltini *et al.*⁶⁴ observed a maximum H₂ production rate followed by a decrease with increasing quantities of olive mill wastewater, suggesting that the reaction was favoured by an increase in sacrificial agents, as shown also in other studies¹², but then at higher wastewater concentrations, there are adverse effects due to too much light absorbance from the wastewater compounds themselves¹⁴.

2.5. Inorganic ions

Different studies have been conducted to analyse the impact of different inorganic ions as solutes in photocatalytic processes. These effects are significantly linked to reaction conditions, but some general causes can be highlighted.

The presence of cations is reported to have some benefits and drawbacks. Focusing on the negative consequences of having cations in solution, it is reported that both monovalent ions such as Na^+ , K^+ and bivalent ions Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} exacerbate the competitive absorption on the surface of the catalyst, blocking scavenger holes and therefore reducing the efficiency of the process⁶⁵.

Regarding anions, their influence on the photocatalytic activity has also been discussed. It is reported that ions such as Cl^- , SO_2^- , SO_4^- , HCO_3^- and CO_3^{2-} , commonly present in water, inhibit the efficiency of the photocatalytic process⁶⁶. It seems that sulphates would be the least concerning of these ions, followed by carbonate, chlorine and then bicarbonate as having the largest effect⁶⁷. There are two possible inhibition mechanisms: the scavenging effect of these ions, which consume the photogenerated holes, and the blocking of active sites on the catalyst surface due to competitive adsorption⁷².

2.6. pH dependence

The influence of pH on the photocatalytic process of generation of H_2 is significant, as it impacts several parameters such as photocatalyst agglomeration and the substrate adsorption of the photocatalyst surface^{14,68}, specifically its electrostatic interaction⁶⁷. Therefore, the process will be most effective when the wastewater's pH is close to the zero-point charge of the catalyst. The study of pH influence on photocatalytic processes is also a great challenge, as it varies during the reaction¹.

Various studies have determined the effect of pH in H_2 production. One study showed that for higher pH values, the surface area value of TiO_2 nanoparticles increases significantly, as illustrated in Table 6⁷⁴.

Table 6: BET surface area (S_{BET}), cumulative surface area (S_{c}), average pore diameter (D_{p}) and volume (V_{p}) for the prepared TiO_2 NPs⁶⁹.

TiO_2 NPs	S_{BET} (m^2/g)	S_{c} (m^2/g)	D_{p} (nm)	V_{p} (cm^3/g)
pH 10	183.6	215.7	10.8	0.50
pH 7.0	119.4	163.6	7.8	0.23
pH 1.6	12.4	12.7	8.4	0.03

However, it is crucial to notice that several other aspects influence the production of H₂. For instance, Figure 4 illustrates the effect of pH on the hydrogen production rate, clearly showing an optimal pH range. The relationship is non-linear, as the H₂ production rate does not increase steadily with rising pH¹.

Figure 4: Influence of pH on the hydrogen production rate using three different alcohols as sacrificial reagents¹.

Considering this, it is recommended to use neutral to basic solutions (pH 6-10)¹, corroborating the fact that in this pH range, the degradability of pollutants also increases, as presented in Figure 5, for methylene blue degradation⁷⁴. Considering the results of that study, the percentage of degradation through time increases for higher pH values. In contrast, other authors suggest using a value closer to neutral pH, since they have observed that, under such conditions, glycerol over a Pt/TiO₂ photocatalyst shows increased hydrogen evolution¹². On the other hand, Speltini *et al.*⁶⁸ demonstrated that for olive mill wastewater over a Pt/TiO₂ (0.5 wt%) catalyst, which has an intrinsic pH of 4.5, an acidic pH (below 4) would achieve higher values of hydrogen evolution. This effect is discussed as a result of weakly acidic pollutants having a higher adsorption rate under acidic conditions⁷¹. It was also observed in other studies, degrading phenolic compounds in real wastewater³.

Considering these various contrasting results, pH should ideally be around neutral values, especially for TiO₂-based photocatalysts. However, the use of alkaline or acidic IWW could also be possible, depending on the IWW composition and the catalytic system, and its use would warrant specific optimisation across pH ranges.

Figure 5: Efficiency of methylene blue photodegradation over TiO₂ nanoparticles prepared at different pH values; 1.6, 7.0 and 10⁶⁹.

2.7. Dissolved Oxygen

The influence of dissolved oxygen is crucial when studying photocatalytic processes such as the one used in SPECTRUM. This parameter plays a significant role in the production of H₂, as well as in the degradation of water pollutants. Dissolved oxygen directly affects the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and influences the recombination of charge carriers⁷⁰.

On one side, the presence of O₂ dissolved in high concentrations (2-5 mg/L, e.g.) in the aqueous solution is essential to increase the degradation of the pollutants, as the oxygen molecules will act as electron scavengers and form superoxide radicals that, further, will react to generate hydroxyl radicals and other ROS, therefore accelerating the process of oxidation of pollutants^{71,72}.

On the other hand, low oxygen concentrations in the aqueous solution minimise electron competition, allowing the photogenerated electron to react with H⁺ ions and produce H₂. It is also very important to note that the presence of sacrificial agents in water is crucial and can reduce the electron scavenging effect of O₂, as these compounds will more rapidly capture the H⁺ ions⁷³.

2.8. Performance indicators of photocatalytic reaction and H₂ cogeneration

To evaluate the efficiency and sustainability of solar photocatalytic hydrogen production using industrial wastewater as a source of sacrificial agents, several key performance indicators have been employed or developed by various authors. These metrics are an

important tool to develop and optimise the photocatalytic process in terms of catalyst materials and various process parameters such as pH, temperature and concentrations of key compounds such as sacrificial agents. Most importantly, they offer insights into the conversion efficiency for hydrogen gas production and subsequent degradation of pollutants, which are two key objectives for the development of this technology. When advancing this technology to utilise a complex matrix such as IWW, it enables a comparison between various IWW and their suitability for this process.

The first performance parameter is the HER. It is a fundamental measure of the photocatalytic activity of a system. It quantifies the amount of hydrogen produced per unit time and often per gram of catalyst and therefore expresses the rate of hydrogen production. This parameter is often important in catalyst development and optimisation when comparing different catalysts or operating conditions under standard illumination.

$$HER = \frac{n_{H_2}}{t} \text{ or } \frac{n_{H_2}}{m_{cat} \times t} \quad (3)$$

Where:

- n_{H_2} is the amount of H_2 produced (μmol or mmol);
- t is the reaction time (h);
- m_{cat} is the mass of catalyst used (g).

In studies using real wastewaters, instead of the rate, authors have often preferred to determine the hydrogen volume or yield (see Table 3). This refers to the total volume or molar amount of H_2 produced during the reaction. It can be normalised to reactor volume, time, or photocatalyst mass depending on the experimental context. Yield is a critical measure of overall productivity. When normalised to sacrificial agent content (e.g., per gram of COD or TOC), it can provide insight into system selectivity and efficiency.

Another performance indicator is the solar-to-hydrogen efficiency (η_{STH}). This represents the fraction of incident solar energy converted into chemical energy stored in molecular hydrogen. This is one of the most fundamental indicators of system viability, especially when evaluating scalability under solar irradiation. This indicator could be used to benchmark the effect of using IWW with solar photocatalytic hydrogen generation systems.

$$\eta_{STH}(\%) = \left(\frac{n_{H_2} \times \Delta H_{H_2}}{P_{solar} \times t \times A} \right) \times 100 \quad (4)$$

Where:

- ΔH_{H_2} is the higher heating value of H_2 in kJ/mol ;
- P_{solar} is the solar irradiance in kW/m^2 ;

- t is the irradiation time in s;
- A is the area exposed to light in m^2 .

However, the solar-to-hydrogen efficiency does not quantify the effect on wastewater remediation. This can be determined via the hydrogen yield per unit of COD removed. This indicator quantifies the amount of hydrogen produced in relation to the COD removed, giving a direct correlation between pollutant oxidation and hydrogen generation.

$$H_2 \text{ Yield (mg/mg COD)} = \frac{m_{H_2}}{\Delta COD} \quad (5)$$

Where:

- m_{H_2} is the mass of hydrogen produced (mg);
- ΔCOD is the COD consumed during the reaction, given as $\Delta COD = (COD_{initial} - COD_{final})$;

This ratio provides insight into the efficiency of electron donation from the sacrificial agents. For olive mill wastewater, a yield of 0.1 mg H_2 per 28 mg COD removed was obtained⁶⁴, even though very little COD decrease was observed indicating incomplete mineralisation under anaerobic photocatalytic conditions.

To characterise the efficiency of wastewater remediation, the COD removal should also be determined. The reduction of COD reflects the degree of organic matter oxidation during the process. Li et al. reported COD reductions of up to 58% after solar photocatalytic treatment⁷⁴.

$$COD \text{ Reduction (\%)} = \left(\frac{COD_{initial} - COD_{final}}{COD_{initial}} \right) \quad (6)$$

Another parameter that might be important when it comes to comparing across different photocatalysts, reactor designs, or light intensities, and is essential for modelling and optimisation is the photodegradation rate¹⁰. This could be determined based on a single pollutant or for COD. It provides a kinetic perspective on pollutant degradation and is often calculated using pseudo-first-order reaction kinetics.

$$\ln \left(\frac{C_0}{C_t} \right) = k \times t \quad (7)$$

Where:

- C_0 is the initial concentration of the pollutant;
- C_t is the concentration at time t ;
- k is the apparent rate constant (min^{-1} or h^{-1});

- t is the time (min or h).

Finally, an important parameter to consider in these photocatalytic systems involving complex matrices and often unknown compound cocktails is the by-product formation⁵³. It is a crucial aspect for assessing environmental safety and the extent of the catalytic reaction. In some cases, hydrogen generation may occur even in the absence of full pollutant mineralisation. For instance, the COD reduction might be insignificant, but the main pollutant has been converted to another by-product that is potentially more harmful or polluting than the initial one. Speltini *et al.* observed no significant COD reduction in a photocatalytic system treating olive mill wastewater, suggesting partial oxidation and the formation of persistent by-products under anaerobic conditions⁶⁴. In this case, there is no consolidated indicator available; however, by-products such as aromatic intermediates or chlorinated compounds can be detected and quantified using analytical techniques, including Gas Chromatography coupled to Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) and High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), or simply through the evolution of TOC or COD analysis. Understanding the nature and toxicity of these intermediates is vital to ensure that the photocatalytic treatment does not transfer pollution from one form to another.

Together, these indicators provide a robust framework for assessing the technical and environmental performance of solar photocatalytic hydrogen production using industrial wastewater. Their combined application facilitates the optimisation of both hydrogen yield and pollutant degradation, while addressing concerns around by-product toxicity and energy efficiency.

3. Available studies of photocatalytic hydrogen cogeneration using real industrial wastewater

There are several examples of photocatalytic H₂ cogeneration exploiting real industrial wastewater, potentializing all the benefits mentioned in Section 1.4.

Salgado et al.⁷⁵ explored the organic content of municipal and industrial wastewaters at acid pH to H₂ generation using a TiO₂/Au (0.5%) photocatalytic process, underlining the influence of the ionic strength to a low yield of H₂ production. The H₂ production using municipal wastewater (MWW), with a conductivity value of 2.0 mS/cm, was higher when comparing to the same test using IWW, with a value of conductivity of 4.86 mS/cm, corroborating the inference that waters with higher conductivity values yields less hydrogen⁷⁵. Additionally, a low production of hydrogen using IWW and MWW was observed and, consequently, a comparison was also established between synthetic solutions of SA and real IWW, resulting that synthetic solutions hold a higher yield of H₂ production, in the same experimental conditions. This highlights the impact of the presence of compounds that can deactivate the catalyst or act as electron scavenger. Furthermore, and although the DOC removal values were rather low, the authors emphasise the positive influence of DOC toward the generation of H₂.

Moinuddin et al.⁷⁶ makes a comparative study between photolysis and photocatalysis using sulphide bearing wastewater. To perform these tests, it was also performed a comparison using two types of wastewaters, the inlet and outlet samples of a effluent treatment unit, and different synthetic wastewaters, all acting as electron trappers. Focusing on the photocatalytic part with indoor conditions and using real wastewaters, different values of photocatalytic hydrogen production were determined using Pt_{2.5}/TiO₂. The values of HER obtained for the inlet and outlet samples were 390 and 220 μmol/g.h, respectively, suggesting that the reduction of the concentration of SA in the effluent treatment negatively impacts the H₂ production, as a relatively high concentration of SA is essential for the process, as established in Section 2.2. By scavenging the holes from SA of the sulphide bearing wastewater, the Pt/TiO₂ photocatalyst can actively inhibit the electron-hole pair recombination process and, therefore, enhance high photocatalytic hydrogen production efficiencies.

Speltini et al.⁶⁴ studies the usage of SA from the olive mill industry in the photocatalytic process of H₂ evolution. There were various parameters evaluated on this paper, including the irradiation time. It was observed that H₂ yield reached a plateau after 4 hours, concluding also that there was some deactivation of the photocatalyst, Pt/TiO₂, probably due to the oil and grease present in the wastewater. Additionally, the pH of the sample was also assessed, observing that lowest pH values led to the highest yield, these being explained due to the high adsorption affinity for the catalyst surface, as mentioned by the authors^{3,13}.

Furthermore, there are other examples of photocatalytic tests using real IWW. Table 7 presents several parameters obtained for the different tests.

Table 7: Examples of photocatalytic hydrogen co-generation studies using real industrial wastewaters.

Industry	System	Reaction time & Volume	HER ($\mu\text{mol/g}\cdot\text{h}$)	H ₂ yield (mmol)	COD* or TOC/DOC (ppm)	COD* or TOC/DOC reduction
Rice Processing ⁷⁷	g-C ₃ N ₄ /Pt(3%), 0.5 g/L, natural sunlight	4 h, -	114	-	-	-
Liquor brewing ³²	VS ₂ /g-C ₃ N ₄ , visible-light	3 h, 0.05 mL	9 628	0.6	-	59%*
Olive Oil ¹⁴	TiO ₂ /Pt, 2 g/L, UV-A	4 h, -	183	0.044	944*	2%
Olive Oil ³	TiO ₂ mesoporous nanopowder, 2 g/L, UV-C	2 h, -	10 600	36	8 410*	87%*
Municipal wastewater ⁷⁸	TiO ₂ /Au(0.5%), 0.2 g/L, natural sunlight	5 h, 25 L	22	-	100	15%
Fruit juice industry ⁷⁸	TiO ₂ /Au(0.5%), 0.2 g/L, natural sunlight	5 h, 25 L	11	-	600	0%
Antibiotic ⁷⁹	In ₂ Se ₃ /Ag ₃ PO ₄ , 0.5 g/L, visible-light	4 h, 0.5 L	4 206	16.8	19.81	82%
Paper mill sulphide-rich ²⁰	Pt _{2.5} /TiO ₂ , 0.375 mg/L, natural sunlight	2 h, 0.4 L	390	-	123 (0.226 - ppm S ²⁻)	-

For instance, there is a study presented in Table 7 that stands out from the others due to the high value of HER achieved. In the first study, concerning the olive mill wastewater testing, several experiments were conducted using different values of catalyst concentration, pH and reaction time. The best result was obtained for an acidic pH and a concentration of TiO₂ of 2 g/L, confirming the high influence of pH and TiO₂ dose loading on the photocatalytic degradation and hydrogen production. Additionally, the authors also suggest that the photocatalytic hydrogen production was enhanced over the large surface area of the mesoporous nano-titania photocatalyst used³. As aforementioned in

Sector 2, the increase in photocatalytic activity is a consequence of the specific surface area, as the reaction rates tend to be greater than the electron-hole recombination, also due to the organic matter, which acts as SA. The COD is also very high in these wastewaters, supporting the need for organic matter as sacrificial agents for the hydrogen production via photocatalytic processes.

Among the several examples presented above, different samples are being tested, which ultimately yield different results. Generally, it is safe to conclude that the HER mainly depends on the parameters described in Section 2, which, ultimately, reflect the overall complex matrix of the IWW.

4. Potential industries and practical information

Photocatalytic processes have been employed to degrade organic pollutants using TiO₂-based photocatalysts. Furthermore, the use of pollutants as sacrificial agents during the photocatalytic hydrogen production has been highlighted, as this approach enhances both the efficiency of hydrogen production in these processes and reduces their costs, while simultaneously lowering the pollutant load in the IWW^{29,40}.

As mentioned earlier, several benefits are associated with using IWW for hydrogen production via photocatalysis. However, SPECTRUM aims to harness solar energy to produce hydrogen while simultaneously decontaminating IWW, combining this with production of heat and power, as the photocatalyst will have a major impact on the yield and efficiency of the subsequent sub-components (PV modules and thermal absorber).

The selection of the IWW for experimental testing of the process should be verified based on four main factors:

1. Potential industries and types of streams from which to collect the samples;
2. Relevant IWW parameters;
3. Pre-treatment steps;
4. Logistical considerations.

4.1. Selection of industries and type of streams

Since the SPECTRUM prototypes are expected to produce heat and electricity, alongside hydrogen, the selected wastewater should come from an industry that can integrate and utilise these energy outputs.

There are several factors to take into consideration when selecting the IWW sample from an industrial site. Another goal of SPECTRUM is to utilise IWW streams that lack treatment methods, are costly to treat, or are not treated at all, thereby adding value to these types of streams. Indeed, it is highly desirable that only pre-treatment, based in suspended solids removal and conventional filtration (i.e. sand filtration or similar), would be necessary. Additionally, it is preferable that the sample is not collected from an end-of-process IWW stream itself, but rather from a by-product stream or a medium to small-volume IWW stream for a proper selection of valuable components as sacrificial agents.

Furthermore, in the context of SPECTRUM, these IWW should contain compounds that are not easily recoverable for other purposes, preferably, and should comply with the parameters outlined in the previous chapter.

IWW biodegradability is a critical issue to address. Photocatalysis processes for cogenerating hydrogen could enhance this parameter, allowing for easier disposal of

treated IWW in sewage. Therefore, non-biodegradable IWW would have an additional value.

No direct relationship has been found between the concentration of organic matter and photo reforming rate, but highly saline wastewater has been found to delay H₂ production⁸⁰. However, organic matter content cannot be so low, as many of the studies include sacrificial agent concentration in the range of tens of mM or higher⁸¹. Therefore, COD concentration > 500 mg/L would be necessary.

Some inorganics as metal sulphides (due to the high concentrations of sulphide) could be also a source of sacrificial agent for the photocatalytic hydrogen evolution. Moreover, S²⁻ also might be found in tannery wastewater as a byproduct of the leather tanning process⁸² which typically involves the use of sulphide-based chemicals

Given the solar aspect of the project, priority is potentially given to industries typical of Mediterranean countries (PT, ES, IT), such as olive transformation, wine production, the textile industry, tanneries, paper mill wastewater, cork boiling wastewater, etc.

Moreover, considering the common characteristics of their effluents, there are additional industries of interest, such as the pharmaceutical industry, the sugar refinery industry, biorefineries (i.e. biodiesel), alcohol and derivatives distillery, and the food industry.

4.2. Possible pre-treatment steps

The primary treatment of wastewater typically involves the use of physical methods, such as flocculation, precipitation, filtration, air flotation, and centrifugation, to remove larger particles, solids, and grease that float on the surface of the wastewater¹⁹. Being a photocatalytic process and taking into account that usual tubular solar photoreactors have a 3-10 cm diameter⁸², TSS and turbidity are key matters. There is limited experience in photocatalysis processes to cogenerate hydrogen at large scale with solar photoreactors, but we could gain insight from other well-known solar photocatalytic processes such as SODIS⁸³. A 30 NTU (Nephelometric Turbidity Unit) could be considered a good "rule of thumb" for the maximum turbidity of wastewater. Later, turbidity will be dramatically affected by photocatalyst particles, which should then be determined on a case-by-case basis. Therefore, the primary treatment of wastewater to remove particles should take this into account.

The pre-treatments to be performed on IWW suitable for their use in the photocatalytic H₂ generation process depend greatly on the type of IWW and the source industry, and typically can include the following pre-treatment steps:

- Coagulation, flocculation and/or sedimentation to remove larger suspended solids;
- Filtration to remove smaller suspended solids to prevent light attenuation¹⁹;

- Dilution to adjust organic load to 0.5–1 g/L for optimal HER⁷⁷;
- pH adjustment (as a last resort) to neutralise strong acidic/alkaline streams using cost-effective agents (e.g., NaOH, H₂SO₄)¹⁹.

Physicochemical treatments based on coagulation/flocculation (C/F) processes reduce or eliminate both colour and turbidity in wastewater. The process involves altering the physical state of certain colloidal particles, converting them into particles that can be separated by sedimentation. This process is carried out by adding specific chemical compounds, known as coagulants and flocculants, to the wastewater, followed by mixing (or agitation) under controlled conditions. Coagulants destabilise the colloidal particles by eliminating the electrical double layers surrounding them, leading to the formation of microscopic nuclei. Flocculants cause microscopic nuclei to agglomerate, forming larger agglomerates called flocs. The result is wastewater with lower colour and turbidity. However, it is important that the C/F process be properly optimised for each specific type of wastewater, since the formation of a very small or light flocs results in insufficient settling and therefore the process may not be effective. Filtration could be the final step to achieve a turbidity level of less than 30 NTU, if necessary. After C/F, a sand filter followed by microfiltration could be the choice to polish the IWW to fit-for-purpose quality ready for the photocatalytic treatment.

4.3. Logistical and supply chain considerations

In addition to the IWW source, characteristics and possible mitigation pre-treatments, other aspects of logistics and supply chain should be considered. These include:

- Sample preservation conditions, either for transport or for storing, in the case of *à priori* testing of possible IWW samples. For example, alcohols or other possible SA could evaporate, other compounds could biodegrade, etc.). This logistical consideration would be important for experimentation, trying to transport in less than 48 h and storing <5°C during maximum four weeks. For industrial implementation of photocatalytic processes to cogenerate hydrogen at a large scale, solar collectors and photoreactors should be installed as close to the source of IWW as possible so as to be connected by a pipeline;
- Sacrificial agents should be compounds soluble in water. Any other non-dissolved organic or inorganic compound will be lost during C/F process;
- Availability of wastewater, including seasonality and day/night patterns;
- Flows produced and if they match the photocatalytic treatment capacity and land area for solar exposure. Selection of suitable streams inside the industry will be a key topic for higher concentration and purity of the sacrificial agent;

- Industry's needs in using hydrogen (purity of H₂ and flow), jointly with heat and electricity.

4.4. Decision steps for selecting the most favourable industrial wastewater candidates for hydrogen production

This section presents a flowchart with a systematic step-by-step decision-making framework that includes various questions for identifying the best possible IWW candidates to be used as sources of sacrificial agents for photocatalytic hydrogen production. It begins by identifying IWWs with high organic content, particularly those rich in alcohols, sugars, organic acids, or sulphides—compounds known to enhance hydrogen evolution. This decision tree provides an initial approach to identifying promising waste streams for sustainable hydrogen production and classifies candidate IWW streams as likely, likely but subject to pre-treatment or testing, unlikely, or unsuitable. The final decision would then need to consider additional IWW characterisation, preliminary testing with the catalyst systems and reactors and all the logistics and supply chain considerations highlighted in section 4.3.

Figure 6: Decision tree on the most favorable industrial wastewater candidates for hydrogen production.

5. Conclusion

The integration of IWW as a source of SA in solar-driven photocatalytic hydrogen (H_2) production presents a compelling dual opportunity: sustainable energy generation and enhanced IWW treatment. This approach leverages the inherent organic and inorganic loads present in IWW, particularly compounds like alcohols, saccharides, organic acids, and sulphides, which act as effective SA, enhancing hydrogen evolution while simultaneously reducing COD and/or increasing pollutant biodegradability and eventually remediating other pollutant parameters.

These guidelines have identified critical parameters influencing the viability of this method, such as organic content (COD, BOD), pH, dissolved oxygen, turbidity, light-scattering compounds, and the presence of inhibitory inorganic ions. Studies suggest that moderate to high concentrations of organic pollutants, when carefully managed, can enhance photocatalytic hydrogen production efficiency. Excessive concentration of SA may hinder light penetration and catalyst activity, while insufficient SA levels would dramatically reduce reaction kinetics. Thus, optimization of this parameter through careful characterisation of SA concentration in SA and eventual dilution with other IWW streams is essential.

Various experimental studies demonstrate that while synthetic SA yield higher hydrogen evolution rates under controlled conditions, real IWW samples—especially from food processing, olive oil production, and fermentation industries—can offer competitive yields with the added benefit of pollutant degradation. These findings affirm the feasibility of using IWW as a low-cost, abundant, albeit seasonally variable feedstock for decentralized hydrogen production.

The techno-economic and environmental advantages of this approach are notable. Photocatalytic systems powered by sunlight can be deployed near the source of wastewater generation, reducing transportation and operational costs while complying with regulatory requirements on wastewater discharge. Nonetheless, the complexity of IWW matrices, variability in composition, and potential for catalyst deactivation underline the need for thorough characterisation, tailored pre-treatment, and careful system design.

Ultimately, these guidelines provide a step-by-step decision-making framework for assessing the suitability of utilising IWW streams as sacrificial agents in photocatalytic hydrogen production. It begins by identifying IWWs with high organic content, particularly those rich in alcohols, sugars, organic acids, or sulphides — compounds known to enhance hydrogen evolution. The next step involves assessing the presence of potential inhibitors (e.g., heavy metals or halides) and key water quality parameters such as COD, pH, turbidity. If preliminary screening is positive, the wastewater can then be evaluated under laboratory-scale photocatalytic testing to determine hydrogen generation potential and pollutant degradation efficiency. Based on these results, the candidate IWW

can be classified as likely, likely but subject to pre-treatment or testing, unlikely or unsuitable. The flowchart ensures a systematic first approach to identifying promising aqueous waste streams for sustainable hydrogen production and IWW pollutant remediation.

Moving forward, further research should focus on reactor scale-up, life-cycle assessments, and the development of robust performance indicators that capture both hydrogen production and IWW pollutant remediation. Future research should also focus on catalyst-adaptive systems to handle IWW variability, as the photocatalytic reactor itself will have a great impact on the yield and efficiency of the subsequent sub-components (PV modules and thermal absorber). Moreover, interdisciplinary collaboration will be crucial to translate laboratory insights into field applications. The SPECTRUM project contributes significantly to this effort by providing practical guidelines and laying the foundation for technology demonstration and deployment across suitable Mediterranean and European industrial sectors.

Harnessing industrial wastewater for photocatalytic hydrogen production represents a step toward circular economy models, where waste streams are transformed into energy vectors, supporting Europe's goals for carbon neutrality and clean energy transition.

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